

Title: New Frontiers in Retail Data Science

Abstract:

Within the backdrop of advancements in big data technologies and in deep learning, the forward thinking retailers has the potential to unleash innovative solutions to their competitive advantage. Broadly speaking, retail analytics and data science has been successful in solving problems across several retail functions, such as market basket analysis (MBA) and online recommenders (collaborative filter), just to name a few.

While some very important have been made over the past decade, we want to introduce new opportunities that arise from combining the “newer” data sources such as social, IoT, mobile, online competitive information, etc., with traditional retail data (e.g. transactional sales, inventory and logistics, and customer loyalty, etc.).

Coupled with advancements in distributed computing systems (Hadoop), and deep learning (GPU) techniques, in addition to this plethora of new available data, this offers an exciting new opportunity for retailers to develop competitive and potentially disruptive solutions in the industry.

Some topics of discussion may include:

- Reinforcement learning and Markov decision processes for Personalization and Recommendations
- Deep learning algorithms for purchase intent/behaviour
- External data enrichment: Impact of social media, weather, or legal/health policies on retail
- Digital & offline marketing attribution
- Cross-channel marketing across retail (store) & Digital (web and mobile)
- Stochastic replenishment and inventory optimization
- Maximizing short term vs long term customer lifetime value

BIOGRAPHY:

Edward Kim is a passionate leader in “big-data science” with 24 years experience in Data Mining, Machine Learning, Parallel & Map-Reduce algorithms, Predictive Modeling, Optimization, Large Scale Analytic Algorithms. Researched and published over 30+ US patent filings in retail science at Teradata, then social marketing at Sysomos, and then customer insights at Indigo. PhD in Computer Science from Simon Fraser University, Rotman MBA, MSc in Electrical Engineering, and BSc in Engineering Science all from University of Toronto.